

The Effect of Lyrical vs. Non-Lyrical Music on Speech Fluency

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April 28, 2023

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Literature Review

Developments and improvements in technology throughout the ages have been accompanied by an increase in music listening. The current generation, many of whom are students, tends to listen to music while performing activities such as learning.

Listening to music while studying can be beneficial as it tends to ease stress and blood pressure while reducing test anxiety (Florida National University, 2019). Crystal Raypole, a writer and editor in the fields of natural sciences and mental health, and Karin Gepp, a medical article reviewer and clinical psychologist in the fields of mood-related difficulties, anxiety, and forensic topics, support this claim. Raypole suggests that listening to music can improve mood and agrees that it reduces stress. Music that one is familiar with can even motivate the listener as it increases dopamine levels (Raypole, 2020).

Mitzi Baker, a Science & Medical Writer at Stanford University School of Medicine, wrote an article on research that claims listening to music can help one pay attention. Her research analyzed the neural networks of participants as they listened to classical symphonies from English late-baroque period composer William Boyce using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) scans. Baker's findings convey that "Music engages the brain over a period of time . . . and the process of listening to music could be a way that the brain sharpens its ability to anticipate events and sustain attention" (Baker, 2007).

Nevertheless, research has also found that listening to music while studying can have adverse effects. In an editorial in *The Music Universe*, a credible music news reporting service currently housing approximately 15,000 music articles, founder Buddy Iahn argues that "listening to music as you study can reduce your productivity levels by at least ten percent." This is because the "changing words and fluctuation of tunes" have the ability to distract the listener

as they try to memorize information (Iahn, 2021). Raypole agrees, claiming that listening to “your favorite tunes” might increase dopamine levels but can interfere with thought processing. She argues that music can negatively impact one’s working memory when performing tasks such as trying to memorize a procedure or a list (Raypole, 2020).

According to Sam Kemmis, a Senior Writer with a Master’s degree in Biology from Binghamton University, the change in productivity while listening to music depends on the music tastes and preferences of the listener. He asserts that “listening to [familiar music] with lyrics . . . can be distracting” (Kemmis, 2019). Therefore, one’s productivity is decreased when he or she listens to songs with lyrics. Van Thompson from the Seattle Post-Intelligencer, an online newspaper that once won the Pulitzer Prize for Public Service, agrees with Kemmis, explaining how music with lyrics activates the language-processing centers of the brain and can cause distractions. However, Thompson also addresses the other major type of music: non-lyrical or instrumental music (Thompson, 2013).

According to Emily Hughes, a mezzo-soprano who holds a Master of Music from the Conservatory of Music of Brooklyn College, instrumental music is “any music that does not include lyrics or words, only . . . musical instruments, such as pianos, guitars, violins, etc.” This type of music is often created for activities like dancing and sports. On the other hand, vocal music is “any music with vocals or singing” (Hughes, 2021). While instrumental music can be soothing to listen to and is universally accepted, it cannot energize an audience and lacks the psychological connection that vocal music possesses. Vocal music is more popular than its counterpart as it often tells a story and conveys an emotion, while the latter usually cannot do this, and even if it does, it is usually to a negligible extent (Hughes, 2021).

Not only does Van Thompson argue that listening to lyrical music while studying can be distracting, but he also claims that instrumental music can have a soothing or relaxing effect on students and is much less distracting than lyrical music (Thompson, 2013). Similarly, Raypole claims that listening to music can lower reading comprehension. As a solution, she suggests avoiding music with lyrics and instead choosing slow, unfamiliar, instrumental music when performing such tasks (Raypole, 2020). To establish that one type of music should be used over the other when performing academic tasks, further research on the differentiated effects of lyrical and non-lyrical music on reading comprehension and language processing has been studied.

Cameron Campbell Miller from the M.A. School Psychology at Rowan University and his advisor, Roberta Dihoff, a professor at Rowan University with a BA in Psychology, MA in Child Development, and PhD in Human Development, tested the effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on reading comprehension as it related to different genres of music. In Miller's study, 72 American undergraduate student participants took the reading comprehension of the Nelson Denny Reading Test while listening to either classical music with lyrics, classical music without lyrics, rock with lyrics, rock without lyrics, or no music. The two genres of music were chosen in accordance with the Mozart Effect, which claims that "classical music, specifically composed by Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart, facilitates cognitive performance" and prejudice against rock music. Songs played in the experimental groups had English lyrics and both lyrical and non-lyrical versions (Miller, 2014).

Descriptive Statistics: Sample Population

Genre	Lyrics	N	Mean	SD
Control	Control	13	15.077	2.139
Classical	Lyrical	13	13.154	2.304
	Non-Lyrical	17	15.294	1.212
Rock	Lyrical	11	14.182	2.400
	Non-Lyrical	18	14.111	2.042

Note. Scores range from 0-18. A higher score indicates more items answered correctly.

Table 1: Results of Cameron Campbell Miller's study.

Miller's results suggest that non-lyrical music is less intrusive than lyrical music while performing a reading comprehension task, but a one-way analysis of variance test showed that the difference was not statistically significant enough to confirm his findings (Miller, 2014).

“The effect of lyrical and non-lyrical background music on different types of language processing - An ERP study” by Eun Kyoung Lee, Sung Eun Lee, and Young Sung Kwon focused on analyzing the effect of listening to lyrical music, non-lyrical music, or silence while processing orthographic, semantic, and syntactic texts. 60 undergraduate students from Seoul National University, split into 3 groups - one listening to lyrical music, another listening to non-lyrical, and the last not listening to music at all - were tested. 30 sentences were created by the researchers, and three grammatically incorrect versions for each accompanied them. 14 unfamiliar songs from various genres were played from the most widely used online music service in South Korea. EEGs were recorded, and allowed the researchers to analyze the brain activity of the participants. The study determined that lyrical music hinders orthographic and syntactic processing but has no effect on semantic processing, while non-lyrical music does not affect all three kinds (Lee et al., 2020).

Various studies that compare the different effects of lyrical music versus non-lyrical music on reading comprehension and language processing, such as the ones discussed above, exist. However, there currently exists no research on the differentiated effects of the two types of music on an important component of language: speech.

In “Language In Brief,” American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA), a professional and scientific credentialing organization for speech-language pathologists, audiologists, and speech scientists, refers to language as a “rule-governed behavior” that includes comprehension, spoken, written, and communication symbol systems (ASHA, 2022). Spoken includes listening and speaking, written includes reading and writing, and communication symbols include American Sign Language.

Speech fluency is a specific component of speech that ASHA refers to as the “continuity, smoothness, rate, and effort in speech production.” They term the use of filler words and repetition of words and phrases as “typical disfluencies or nonfluencies” (ASHA, 2022). According to Emily Duvall, Aimee Robbins, Thomas Graham, and Scott Divett, some causes of the use of filler words include divided attention, infrequent words, and nervousness (Duvall et al., 2014). Such causes are usually aggravated while listening to music. They argue that disfluencies can negatively affect the credibility and have a negative impact on the understanding of the listener.

In order to fill a gap in the body of knowledge regarding the differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on language, a study similar to Cameron Miller’s must be performed on speech. To address the problem of nonfluencies in speech negatively impacting credibility in a growing population of students, speech fluency can be focused on. This raised the question: How does listening to lyrical vs. non-lyrical music affect speech fluency in high school juniors?

The study was limited to high school juniors due to sampling in such a manner during data collection. Based on the other studies present in the body of knowledge, the hypotheses are as follows

1. The presence or absence of music will have an impact on speech fluency
2. Listening to lyrical music will have a greater negative impact on speech fluency than non-lyrical music will.

Methodology

In order to address the question two-dimensionally, a mixed-method approach was used. Cameron Miller studied the effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on reading comprehension, and accordingly, the participants in his study were randomly assigned into groups who all took a reading comprehension test while they listened to either lyrical, non-lyrical, or no music (Miller, 2014). Researchers from the Seoul National University had their participants split into groups the same way, and these participants processed orthographic, semantic, and syntactic texts while listening to their assigned music (Lee et al., 2020). Adopting these methods, this study included a controlled experiment where the participants performed a speech fluency test while listening to either lyrical, non-lyrical, or no music. A controlled experiment was conducted as the study attempted to determine whether a causal relationship existed between two variables. Studying the effect of manipulating a variable, type of music in this case, on another variable, speech fluency here, allows one to find a possible connection between the two. Issues with using an experimental research method include possible ethical risks and privacy concerns. However, measures were taken to ensure that these would not be significant and that possible harm to participants is averted.

The participants for the experiment were all Hagerty High School 11th graders enrolled in AP English Language and Composition under one specific teacher. Students who participated were given physical Informed Consent Forms (Appendix C) and a brief synopsis of the experiment. The Informed Consent Forms served as documentation of parental permission for the volunteers under the age of 18. The participants had to return their completed Informed Consent Forms before the time of the experiment. They were told that they have the right to stop participating in the experiment at any given time and that no personally identifiable information would be collected during the study. The students were also informed that their signed consent forms and data would be stored in a password-protected Google Folder. This file will be archived for 3 years, and after that, it will be deleted for participant safety and privacy reasons.

Figure 1: Differences between the three groups present in the experiment.

After recruitment was complete, the sample population was divided into three groups - Group A, Group B, and Group C - using simple random sampling. The specific days for each group, accompanied by their type of group and music, are present in Figure 1. The experimental groups each tested on different days so that fewer students were present at the experiment site, which was the AP English Language and Composition teacher's room, at a time. This was aimed to reduce any discomfort in participants due to nervousness and/or social anxiety while speaking in front of peers. The participants were individually labeled with their group letter and their place in the group as they entered the experiment site. For example, if a student was in Group C and the sixth one to enter the site, they were labeled Participant C6. This allowed for the protection of the privacy of participants as they did not have to provide any identifying information, such as their names and ages. At approximately 2:30 PM on each experiment day, the experiment site's doors were locked to ensure the safety of the students from extraneous hazards.

After the participants were ready, the purpose of the study was reiterated and the experiment's design was explained. The students would play a variation of the Ah, Um Game, a group game that can help players break the habit of using unprofessional and unneeded filler words, either in silence or while listening to lyrical music or non-lyrical music ("How to play The Ah, Um Game", n.d.). A few common examples of filler words, which were recognized in the experiment, include "Like", "Umm/Uh/Er", and "So basically", ("So, um... Are you ready to learn English filler words?", 2021).

In the original game, a volunteer starts in a small group of players. Players are randomly assigned a topic from a list of speaking prompts. A player starts talking about the topic for one full minute and should attempt not to use any filler words. If they proceed to use a filler word, they are eliminated from the game. Given a person does not say any filler words, they are

promoted to the next round. Winners of the game are the players who do not use any filler words (“How to play The Ah, Um Game”, n.d.). In the variation, players are given 30 seconds to speak on a randomly assigned speaking prompt (Appendix D). They are not eliminated if they use filler words, but the number of times they use such words is counted.

Music was played through speakers located above the podium where the participants stood when speaking. The song played during Group A’s experiment was “Doin’ Just Fine” by Hudson Moore (Appendix E). This song was selected because of its genre and publication year. Marie Charlotte Götting published her research on “Favorite music genres among consumers in the United States as of July 2018, by age group” on Statista, a credible statistics publishing company that has a database of more than a million statistics on more than 80,000 topics. In an online survey administered in July 2018, available to American music listeners above the age of 16, she asked, “Which of the following types of music do you generally like?”, and the respondents were given a list of music genres to select. The survey responses conveyed that Country/Western music was one of the least favored music genres among teenagers (Götting, 2021). Prior exposure to a song could be a confounding variable that impacts the experiment, and to avoid this, contemporary songs from popular genres were not considered when choosing a song. Hudson Moore’s “Doin’ Just Fine” is a song that falls under the Country/Western genre, which is not a popular genre for the age group. Combined with its old age, as it was published in 2013, teenage preferences for the song’s genre limit the number of participants who have been exposed to the song.

To avoid any extraneous effects choosing a different song might have, Group B’s experiment also used “Doin’ Just Fine” by Hudson Moore. However, a non-lyrical version of the song was required. While “Hudson Moore - Doin' Just Fine (Official Lyric Video)” could be

played directly from Moore’s music platforms during Group A’s experiment, a non-lyrical version of it did not exist at the time the experiment was conducted (Moore, 2013). To solve this issue, lyric remover software was used (“Vocal Remover and Isolation”, n.d). A downloaded version of the song was input into the software, and the modified audio file it output was used during Group B’s experiment.

As each participant responded to their prompt, the number of times they used filler words and their label were recorded in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The mean number of filler words used by participants was calculated for each group. This was performed by adding up the number of filler words used by all the students from a group and dividing this value by the number of students in the group. To calculate the average number of filler words used by a Group A participant, for example, the following equation was used.

$$x = \frac{fA1 + fA2 + fA3 + fA4 + fA5 + fA6 + fA7 + fA8 + fA9 + fA10}{nA}$$

In the formula above, x is the average number of filler words used by a Group A participant, $fA\#$ is the number of filler words used by participant $A\#$, and nA is the number of participants in Group A.

The standard deviation for the number of times filler words were used by participants for each group was also calculated using the results of the experiment. “Standard Deviation Formula and Uses vs. Variance” is an article in Investopedia, a financial education publication webpage known for its high-quality content and scholarly works. The article’s author, Marshall Hargrave, states that standard deviation is “a statistic that measures the dispersion of a dataset relative to its mean and is calculated as the square root of the variance” (Hargrave, 2022). In other words, it is

the spread from the mean of the dataset. To calculate the standard deviation of the number of filler words used by a Group A participant, for example, the following equation was used.

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(fA\# - x)^2}{nA - 1}}$$

In the formula above, SD is the standard deviation of the number of filler words used by a Group A participant, $fA\#$ is the number of filler words used by participant $A\#$, x is the average number of filler words used by a Group A participant, and n is the number of participants in Group A.

The mean and standard deviation of all the groups were then compared to see how listening to lyrical music affects speech fluency differently than non-lyrical music. To test for statistically significant differences, bar graphs with standard error of the mean bars were made. Microsoft's Excel software was used on the data recorded in the spreadsheet to create the

graphs.

Figure 2: Overlapping in the standard error of the mean bars on bar graphs

If the error bars do not overlap, one can say that there is a statistically significant difference between the data. However, if they do overlap, there is no statistically significant difference present (“Interpreting Error Bars”, n.d.).

Results

After the experimentation for the experimental groups and the control group, a spreadsheet containing raw data was constructed (Appendix A). Participants who were either

previous or active students in Public Speaking Classes, most commonly Debate, were marked with an “X” in the Public Speaking column. A new spreadsheet was created to record the filtered data after removing the data associated with the marked participants (Appendix B).

The mean and the standard deviation from the mean were computed for each of the groups from the spreadsheet for filtered data. Group A’s participants used, on average, 4.63 filler words, with a standard deviation of 3.36 words. Group B’s participants averaged 4.73 filler words with a standard deviation of 1.90 words, and Group C’s participants averaged 5.10 filler words with a standard deviation of 2.08 words.

Figure 3: Bar labeled 1 represents lyrical music, 2 for non-lyrical music, and 3 is no music.

The bar graphs with standard error of the mean bars above were created using Microsoft Excel spreadsheet software to test for statistical significance. The average number of filler words used by participants for each group were inscribed into the bars.

Figure 4: The standard error of the mean bars for Group A and Group B overlap.

The average number of filler words used by Group A's participants, 4.63 ± 3.36 words, is less than the average number of filler words used by Group B's participants, 4.73 ± 1.90 words. However, it cannot be claimed that the difference in the use of filler words between the two groups is statistically significant as the standard error of the mean bars of Bar 1 and 2 overlap.

Figure 5: The standard error of the mean bars for Group A and B do not overlap with Group C.

As the standard error of the mean bars for both Bar 1 and 2 do not overlap with the standard error of the mean bar on Bar 3 and the mean number of filler words used by Group C's participants, 5.10 ± 2.08 words, is greater than the mean number of filler words used by Group A and Group B's participants, the difference in the use of filler words between groups where music is and is not played is statistically significant.

Discussion

Even though the average number of filler words used by a participant listening to non-lyrical music was more than the average number of filler words used by a participant listening to lyrical music in the experiment, there is no statistically significant difference between the two, as their standard error of the mean bars does overlap, as seen in Figure 4. This result rejects this project's second hypothesis and disproves the common idea that lyrical music is more intrusive than non-lyrical music when performing a language-related task. However, the inclusion of the control group confirms the project's first hypothesis. The average number of filler words used by a participant not listening to music is greater than both the average number of filler words used by a participant listening to non-lyrical music and the average number of filler words used by a participant listening to lyrical music. There is a statistically significant difference in the data as the standard error of the mean bar for the group not listening to music does not overlap with the standard error of the mean bar for the groups either listening to lyrical or non-lyrical music, as shown in Figure 5. Therefore, while there are no differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on high school juniors, the presence or absence of music does impact the speech fluency of students.

The findings from this study will allow speakers, teachers, students, and other professionals in the field of education and speech to enhance their speaking skills during

speeches through the use of music. As the study's scope is on high school juniors and the experiment is based on answering prompts from a podium, the findings will be especially useful when 11th-grade students need to make presentations in front of their peers. Douglas R. Seals, a Professor of Integrative Physiology at the University of Colorado Boulder, and McKinley E. Coppock, a Graduate Student at the same school, state in "We, um, have, like, a problem: excessive use of fillers in scientific speech" that "fillers have potentially negative implications for optimal career development and professional success." These claims align with Emily Duvall and colleagues' findings as discussed before. An excessive use of fillers can also hinder one's audience to comprehend what the speaker is trying to convey, as it becomes hard for the audience to "concentrate, hold interest, and absorb the presenter's key points" (Seals & Coppock, 2022).

As this study found that the presence of music positively impacted speech fluency and improved speech, listening to music while in professional conferences and conversations reduces the number of filler words used, effectively helping avoid such problems from occurring.

The findings relate to findings from Cameron Campbell Miller's study on the effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on reading comprehension. Miller made three hypotheses during his research, the first of which claimed that "the control group without music would have different levels of comprehension than music groups, but the scores of the different music groups would vary." His second hypothesis was that "lyrical music . . . would have a greater negative impact on reading comprehension than non-lyrical music." Miller accepted his first hypothesis and rejected his second hypothesis. The findings from this study match Miller's as both the studies' control groups were different from the experimental groups, with the average values of the latter being different. Similar to this experiment's data analysis, the difference between the effect of

lyrical and non-lyrical music was not statistically significant enough to confirm the hypothesis (Miller, 2014).

However, these findings did not comply with Eun Kyoung Lee, Sung Eun Lee, and Young Sung Kwon's findings from "The effect of lyrical and non-lyrical background music on different types of language processing - An ERP study." The researchers found that instrumental music coupled with no music, while this study found that instrumental music coupled with lyrical music. They state, "participants were equally sensitive to linguistic errors when there was instrumental music playing in the background and when there [were] no auditory stimuli at all" (Lee et al., 2020). The findings for speech fluency say otherwise, as there is a statistically significant difference between the average number of filler words used by a participant listening to non-lyrical music and the average number of filler words used by a participant not listening to music.

Limitations

One must note that some limitations in the study could have influenced the findings. The simple random sampling of participants into three groups led to the control group, or group listening to no music, having one more participant than both experimental groups. However, after participants who were either previous or active Debate students were removed from the data, the control group had one less participant than both experimental groups. Unequal sample sizes can cause variance in data and not allow generalization to the population. The different groups all had to participate after school on different days, which opens the experiment up to a few confounding variables. Participants' school schedules differ day-to-day, and incidents that could have occurred during school might influence their mood, which in turn affects their speech and speech fluency. Another limitation is the restriction of participants to only 11th graders in

Advanced Placement English Language and Composition students. The students from this class are challenged more than students in the same English classes in the same grade: English 3 Standard and English 3 Honors. This could cause them to have better speaking skills than the students from the same grade in other English classes, negatively impacting generalization to the population. The study was initially planned with an English 3 Honors teacher and English 3 Honors students, as the latter would be a medium between English 3 Standard and AP English Language and Composition. However, she had to cancel her help with the experiment due to emergencies. Without any other English 3 Honors teachers to contact, the study had to be set up with an AP English Language and Composition teacher and AP English Language and Composition students.

Future Research

While this study has helped find that there is no difference in the effect of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on speech fluency, there are still some gaps that must be filled in the body of knowledge on the topic of speech fluency as it relates to music. One of these is the effect of different genres. The results might have answered the question of how listening to lyrical vs. non-lyrical music affects speech fluency in high school juniors, but the answer could be influenced by the genre of music used during experimentation. Future research in the field could assign different genres of music to different experimental groups and test how these genres have an effect on speech fluency.

There are also gaps that must be filled when it comes to the topic of differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on language. Speech fluency is one of the numerous parts of speech (ASHA, 2022). There are still aspects, such as cohesiveness and speaking vocabulary, that can be explored. When initially exploring the effects of music on language, research on the

differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on reading comprehension and language processing could be found, but not on speech or writing. While this study delved into the effects of the two types of music on speech, their effect on writing and its specific aspects, such as spelling and grammar, has still not been discovered.

Conclusion

To address a gap in the body of knowledge regarding the differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on language, the effect of the two types of music on speech fluency was studied. It was hypothesized that the presence or absence of music would impact speech fluency and that lyrical music would have a greater negative impact on the specific component of speech than non-lyrical music would. A controlled experiment was performed, and the results were analyzed using bar graphs with standard error of mean bars. The findings from this study fail to support the idea that there are differentiated effects of lyrical vs. non-lyrical music on 11th-grade students. However, it does suggest that the presence or absence of music does impact the speech fluency of students. The findings can potentially help high school juniors to reduce the number of filler words they use when presenting and speaking, improving their credibility and the audience's comprehension of the topic.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Raw Data Spreadsheet

Participant Label	# of Filler Words Used	Public Speaking
A1	3	
A2	4	
A3	7	
A4	3	X
A5	4	
A6	0	
A7	2	
A8	3	
A9	2	
A10	3	X
A11	12	
A12	5	X
A13	7	
A14	7	
B1	5	X
B2	5	
B3	4	
B4	10	
B5	3	
B6	4	
B7	6	X
B8	3	X
B9	5	
B10	3	
B11	4	
B12	5	
B13	5	
B14	4	
C1	8	
C2	4	X
C3	3	X
C4	4	X
C5	2	
C6	3	
C7	7	
C8	7	
C9	5	
C10	7	
C11	5	
C12	3	
C13	3	X
C14	4	
C15	5	X

Appendix B: Filtered Data Spreadsheet

Participant Label	# of Filler Words Used
A1	3
A2	4
A3	7
A5	4
A6	0
A7	2
A8	3
A9	2
A11	12
A13	7
A14	7
B2	5
B3	4
B4	10
B5	3
B6	4
B9	5
B10	3
B11	4
B12	5
B13	5
B14	4
C1	8
C5	2
C6	3
C7	7
C8	7
C9	5
C10	7
C11	5
C12	3
C14	4

Appendix C: Informed Consent Forms

Human Informed Consent Form

Instructions to the Student Researcher(s): An informed consent/assent/permission form should be developed in consultation with the Adult Sponsor, Designated Supervisor or Qualified Scientist.

This form is used to provide information to the research participant (or parent/guardian) and to document written informed consent, minor assent, and/or parental permission.

- When written documentation is required, the researcher keeps the original, signed form.
- Students may use this sample form or may copy ALL elements of it into a new document.

If the form is serving to document parental permission, a copy of any survey or questionnaire must be attached.

Student Researcher(s): Aaditya Balasubramaniyan

Title of Project: How does listening to lyrical vs. non-lyrical music affect speech fluency in high school students

You are being asked to volunteer to participate in this science project. If you would like to participate, please sign in the appropriate area below.

Purpose of the project:

To find whether listening lyrical vs. non-lyrical music affects one's speech fluency while speaking on a random topic

If you participate, you will be asked to:

Identify whether you have participated in speech class such as Debate. If no, speak on a random topic for 30 seconds while listening to either a song, an instrumental version of the song, or no music.

Time required for participation:

10 to 15 minutes

Potential Risks of Study:

A risk involved in this project is discomfort in participants due to nervousness and/or social anxiety while speaking in front of others. Classroom doors will be locked in order to ensure safety from extraneous

Benefits:

The results from this study will help find the optimal type of music to listen to while presenting in class.

How confidentiality will be maintained:

No identifiable information will be collected and your responses will be secured in a locked Google Drive which will be deleted in 3 years. I will abide by all the rules of the Belmont Report.

If you have any questions about this study, feel free to contact: 5923944831@student.myscps.us

Adult Sponsor/QS/DS Angela Campbell Phone/email angela_campbell@scps.k12.fl.us

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. There will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate, stop participating, or refuse to answer any question.

By signing this form I am attesting that I have read and understand the information above and I freely give my consent/ assent to participate or permission for my child to participate.

Adult Informed Consent or Minor Assent

Date Reviewed & Signed _____
(mm/dd/yy)

Research Participant Printed Name _____

Signature: _____

Parental/Guardian Permission (if applicable)

Date Reviewed & Signed _____
(mm/dd/yy)

Parent/Guardian Printed Name _____

Signature _____

Appendix D: Speaking Prompts

1. What is your favorite movie and why?
2. What is your favorite sport and why?
3. What has been the best book you've read this year? Explain.
4. If you were an animal, what would you be and why?
5. What's your favorite day of the week? Explain.
6. Would you rather be the richest person, the smartest person, or the most beautiful person?
Why?
7. Would you prefer to read a book or watch a movie? Explain.
8. What is your favorite animal and why?
9. What is your favorite food? Explain.
10. What is the craziest thing you would like to try? Explain.
11. If you could live anywhere in the world, where would you choose? Why?
12. If you could have a superpower, what power would you choose? Why?
13. If you could talk to one species of animal, which would you choose? Why?
14. What is your favorite holiday? Why?
15. Are you a morning or night person? Explain.

Appendix E: Hudson Moore's Doin' Just Fine Link + Lyrics

Link: <https://youtu.be/9MzFLwLEaT8>

Lyrics:

I don't see you much these days,

But I hear you're doin' fine.

I remember the tears down your face

When you told me goodbye.

Baby girl, that's alright

Cause I got good company and my trouble's outside

And I'm...

Sittin' here with all of my friends

Drinkin' beer like the night won't end

Red wine in a Dixie cup

All night 'til the sun comes

up I think I've made up my

mind I don't need you in my

life I'm doin' just fine

You think you got it figured out,

You got me on lock down,

I tell you girl, I moved on.

And now you're tryin' to,

You can't understand why you left me.

Ooh, you're comin' back around.

I should've known you'd me wrong.

I got a lot to make up for the time that I was gone.

So I'm...

Sittin' here with all of my friends

Drinkin' beer like the night won't end

Red wine in a Dixie cup

All night 'til the sun comes up

I think I've made up my mind (yes I did)

I don't need you in my life

I'm doin' just fine

Pretty girls on the inside

Dancing in the kitchen with a bottle of wine

Sittin' here with a beer in my hand, couple of

boys And they do keg stands

Blonde-haired girl lookin' my way
Grab me by the hand, take her up the staircase
Don't know her name, she don't know mine
Hell I don't even know her, she's so fine

Sittin' here with all of my friends
Drinkin' beer like the night won't end
Red wine in a Dixie cup
All night 'til the sun comes up
I think I've made up my mind
I don't need you in my life,
oh Yes I've made up my mind
I'm doin' just fine